

A New Syntactic Foam Manufacturing Method and Study on Its Properties

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Abstract

Hollow particle filled composites, called syntactic foams, are widely used in deep sea applications. The traditional way of producing syntactic foam is to embed glass hollow sphere into a mixture of epoxy hardener solution and then mix them until complete mixing. The mixture is degassed for several minutes and cast in mould at last. This method is in the mainstream position according to statistics of published literature. In recent years, the second way to produce the syntactic foams is to inject the resin into a closed mould by a high injection pressure in which the hollow glass microspheres are filled. This method need resin injection facilities and defined as resin transfer moulding (RTM) which is commonly used as a technology for the manufacture of FRP composites.

The present study focuses on a new manufacturing method involving syntactic foams with low gas porosities or entrapped voids which can be called Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI). VARI processing is very common in FRP industry, but there are no published literature reports on how to produce syntactic foams by VARI. The porosity inside of the syntactic foams can be controlled at a low level without any additional impressed injection pressure but a vacuum pump.

Syntactic foams of $500\text{kg/m}^3 \sim 600\text{kg/m}^3$ were produced by changing the volume percentage of hollow glass spheres using the processing of VARI in this paper. The compressive property is from 35MPa to 49MPa. These syntactic foams can meet the demand of 4900m sea water depth. Little porosity could be found from the

cross-section photograph of SEM. Results indicated that the higher volume content of hollow microspheres led to lower resin penetration rate under given conditions of temperature, injection pressure and resin type. Two kinds of studied microspheres show a similar trend with increased filler content.

Keywords: Syntactic Foam, VARI, Hollow glass microspheres

1. Introduction

Epoxy Syntactic foams are low density composite materials synthesized by dispersing hollow microspheres in a matrix material [1]. The hollow particles may be made of polymer, ceramic, carbon or metal. The most popular particle used in syntactic foam is hollow glass sphere. Syntactic foam is widely used in applications of ROVs (Autonomous Underwater Vehicles), AUVs (Remotely Operated Vehicles) and submersibles for its low density, high rigidity and compressive strength. The closed pore structure gives advantage of lower moisture absorption compare to utilization of other polymeric foams. Syntactic foam products are also used in aerospace industries as cores for sandwich structures and as a repair and replacement for existing honeycomb structures.

The measured density of syntactic prepared by traditional way is normally lower than the theoretical density because some air bubbles are entrapped in the resin system during the fabrication of syntactic foams. The entrapped air forms voids in the matrix resin, which are called matrix porosity. The existence of porosity decreases the mechanical property of the syntactic foams. Presences of hollow spheres in the matrix make syntactic foams a two-phase material [Fig. 1a]. Existence of entrapped air makes the syntactic foams a three-phase material [Fig. 1b]. How to remove the bubbles inside the syntactic foam has been a hot topic.

Fig.1. A representative sketch showing (a) the two-phase structure involve microballoon spheres and the matrix, and (b) three phase structure due to the presence of entrapped gas[2].

The traditional way of producing syntactic foam is to embed glass hollow sphere into a mixture of epoxy hardener solution and then mix them until complete mixing. The mixture is degassed for several minutes and cast in molds at last. This method is in the mainstream position according to statistics of published literature. In recent

years, the second way to produce the syntactic foams is to inject the resin into a closed mould by a high injection pressure in which the hollow glass microspheres are filled. This method need resin injection facilities and defined as resin transfer moulding (RTM). RTM is commonly used as a technology for the manufacture of advanced FRP composite structures.

The present paper focuses on a new manufacturing method involving syntactic foam with low gas porosities or entrapped voids which can be called Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI). It is very common to use VARI processing in FRP composites, but there is no published literature reports how to produce syntactic foams by the processing of VARI. There are many merits to prepare syntactic foams using this processing. An advantage is that the porosity can be controlled at a low level without any additional impressed injection pressure but a vacuum pump. The process of resin impregnating and air bubbles discharge is simultaneous. The viscosity of the resin should be very low; otherwise, the flow distance would be very short and the hollow glass microsphere would not be fully impregnated. Secondly, by virtue of VARI a large-scale syntactic foam production can be made easily for it does not need any big auxiliary equipment. Using VARI techniques with hollow glass microspheres reinforcements provides additional technological, ecological and environmental benefits.

2. Experimental

2.1 material

Scotchlite glass microballoon spheres, manufactured and supplied by 3M, are used in synthesizing these foams. Two different types of hollow glass microspheres K1 and K20 were used as fillers. Properties of the microspheres are listed in table1. The values were obtained from 3M. The average outer diameters of the two kinds are nearly the same.(table 1)

Table 1. Properties of microballoon spheres used in synthesizing syntactic foams

Rank	Compressive strength (MPa)	True particle density	Outer diameter (μm)			
	90% reservation	(g/cc)	10%	50%	90%	maximum
K1	1.72	0.125	30	65	110	120
K20	3.45	0.200	30	65	110	120

The specification of matrix epoxy resin supplied by DOW is given in table 2. Epoxy resin AIRSTONE 760E is a diglicidyl ether of bisphenol A based resin. AIRSTONE 766H is an amine based hardener, also manufactured by Dow Chemical Company.

Table 2. Properties of epoxy resin used in fabricating syntactic foams

property	AIRSTONE 760E Epoxy resin	AIRSTONE 766H Hardener
Viscosity at 25°C (mPa s) ASTM D-445	1400	14
Density at 25°C (g/cc) ASTM D-452	1.16	0.94
Parts by weight	100	32

2.2 Experimental procedures

A harden straight translucent plastic tube with a length of 14cm was prepared for being packed with hollow glass microspheres. The filling part is 10cm. The outer and inner diameter is 12mm and 10mm, respectively. A scale label was adhered to the tube surface. Two layers of peel ply were adhere to the tip of a straight union joint with outside thread and then inserted into the pipeline to make sure that the hollow glass spheres could not pass through the peel ply. A weighed quantity of hollow glass microspheres was added into the pipeline. The container should be sealed and shaken vigorously for 2~3 minutes after the microspheres were added. A smooth stick was used to pack hollow glass microspheres inside the tube in order to make the amount reach a specified volume percentage.

The pipeline was connected to resin container one side and the other side was connected to vacuum pump at last. Experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1. The sealing condition should be checked carefully to ensure no gas leakage before the experiment was started. During the resin infusion process, the catalyzed thermoset epoxy resin was sucked into a pipeline mould cavity using a vacuum pump. A stopwatch was used to record the time when the resin flow arrived at the definite scale on the pipeline surface. Flow front characteristics on the surface of the preform are also recorded using a video camera.

By adding different amounts of microspheres to the pipeline, syntactic foams with various densities were thus created.

Fig.2. Schematic representation of the experimental setup

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Physical properties

Samples of the specimens were measured after taking out from the pipeline. Figure 3 show the length and appearance of the syntactic foam. The hollow particles were fully impregnated by the epoxy resin. It can be seen that all the samples have a smooth finish without any obvious defects.

Fig.3 Two images showing the Syntactic foam taken out from the mould

The densities of the syntactic foam were tested as specified in ISO Standard 1183-2. A large deviation was appeared between the calculated densities and the actual densities as shown in table 3.

Table 3. Details of the syntactic foam taken out from the mould

Type	Particle weight	Calculated Vol (%)	Calculated Density (g/cm ³)	Actual Density (g/cm ³)
K1	0.6002	58.8	0.5707	0.6436
	0.7102	69.4	0.4554	0.5901
	0.8001	79.1	0.3611	0.5340
K20	1.1096	68.7	0.4932	0.5699
	1.2233	77.9	0.4208	0.5492
	1.3584	86.5	0.3348	0.5024

SEM method was used to analyze the internal structure in order to find the mechanism of the deviation. Specimens were coated with a layer of gold in a sputter coating unit prior to examining in scanning electron microscope.

Fig.4 SEM cut section image of K1 58.8 vol% specimen

It can be seen from the cut section's SEM micrograph of the Syntactic foam that many hollow particles crashed before resin infusion and leading to the increase of void percentage. The inside room of the crashed hollow particles was filled with epoxy resin resulted in more injection amount than the calculated quantity. The arrow with the letter of A denotes the crashed hollow particles.

Optical microscope was used to compare the amount of crashed hollow particles between the syntactic foams made of K20 with different volume percentage of hollow particles as it seen in Fig.5. The Calculated volume percentages are as follows: a, e is 68.7%, b, f is 77.9%, c, g is 86.5%.

The higher hollow particle percentage result in more crushed ones. This explains the deviation of density. Excess hollow particles were added into the pipeline

Fig.5 Optical microscope of the cut section image

The percentage of hollow glass microspheres' fracture fragment enhance when the filler quantity increases. This leads to a deviation on the calculation density and the real density.

The inner densities of different segments for one kind of syntactic foam are inconsistent. The segment close to the inlet is denser than the segment close to outlet.

3.2 Analysis and calculation on the permeation rate

3.2.1 Permeation mechanism

Permeability is an important fundamental property used in the study of VARI. This depends up on reinforcement architecture, porosity, resin properties, processing conditions, mould design and part geometry. The resin properties affecting the permeability are viscosity, surface tension and contact angle [3]. Permeability is defined by the well known Darcy's law.

For isotropic materials the flow behavior can be same along all the directions. The hollow glass microspheres can be treated as isotropic and the resin would propagate in the preform with flow front having a circular shape [4]. The permeability process obeys the Darcy's law when the resin flow in the mould filled with hollow glass microspheres.

permeability is given by equation:

$$u_i = \frac{K_{ij} \partial P}{\eta \partial x_i} \quad (1)$$

Where u_i is permeability velocity. $\frac{\partial P}{\partial x_i}$ is the pressure reducing value in a certain direction. η is the resin viscosity at a certain temperature. K_{ij} is the Permeability coefficient.

The fluid front location is a function of distance and time, $S(X_i, t) = 0$, if the maximum length of the mold is L and L is a function of X_i , then the permeability time can be defined as:

$$t = \frac{L^2 (1-V_f)\eta}{2\Delta PK} \quad (2)$$

In this formula: t is the permeability time; L is the flow distance, V_f is the hollow glass microspheres volume fraction, ΔP is pressure drop value within the distance of L , which is equal to an atmospheric pressure in this paper. K is coefficient of permeability.

The fluid is injected into the tube at a constant atmospheric pressure. The resin flow time through the perform glass microspheres at the corresponding scale mark is recorded.

3.2.2 Permeability rate

The maximum packing factor with the sphere of same size is 0.74. The volumetric of resin system to microballoon spheres in the structure work out to be 0.35. Consequently the density of the syntactic foam would be 504 kg/m^3 . The packing factor may exceed the value of 0.74 due to a wide range of size distribution

of microballoon spheres. The size scale of K1 and K20 microspheres from 3M is from $30\mu\text{m}$ to $120\mu\text{m}$.

The packing density of K1 is 0.083g/cm^3 and K20 is 0.14g/cm^3 . The smallest volume content of K1 and K20 is 64.1% and 70.3% respectively which are measured by vibration. Spheres agglomerate into a bulk inside the pipeline because of suction of the vacuum and there will be a void room if the particles volume is lower than the smallest value. This room would be occupied by the neat resin when the resin is injected into the mould as seen from Fig 6.

The flow rate decreased with the increasing of microsphere volume content as it been seen from fig 6. Different types of particles with the similar volume content have almost the same permeability velocity. The permeability curve of 58.8 vol% and the 69.4 vol% of K1 and 68.7 vol% of K20 are coincident.

Fig 6 Flow rate versus position for Darcian flow under constant pressure injection

3.3 Compression tests

Compression tests on the syntactic foam were performed on specimens of $\varnothing 10 \times 15$ mm column according to the test standard of ASTM.

Fig7. Relationship between Calculated Microsphere Volume Fraction and compressive strength of syntactic foam

The compressive strength of syntactic foam made of K20 is higher than K1 when they have similar particle volume percentage (Fig.7). This is something understood well by the mixture rule because the compressive strength of K20 is higher than K1. The syntactic foam made of the same type of particles with higher hollow particle percentage result in lower compressive strength.

4. Conclusions

From the results presented in this paper, it can be concluded that the VARI method could be used for preparing syntactic foam and it has been found to be effective in reducing the void content than the mixture-casting processing. Little porosity could be found from the cross-section SEM photograph. Higher volume content of hollow microspheres led to lower resin penetration rate under given conditions of temperature, injection pressure and resin type. Two kinds of studied microspheres show a similar trend with increased filler content. Due to the existence of crushed hollow glass spheres and its fragment, calculation density and measurement density of syntactic foams were not coincident very well. Density distribution inside of the syntactic foam is not uniform. The inlet part has a greater density than the outlet part because the crushed glass debris subsided into the bottom when the pipeline was shaken vigorously.

Syntactic foams of $500\text{kg/m}^3 \sim 600\text{kg/m}^3$ have been produced whose compressive property are from 35MPa to 49MPa. These syntactic foams can meet the demand of 4900m sea water depth.

The present study is focused on how to manufacture the syntactic foam with the method of VARI and the further research is to decrease the broken rate of the hollow glass particles. Other kind of particles may be introduced into the syntactic foam material systems in order to occupy the inside room of broken particles.

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